

IMPROVING THE TAXATION OF INCOME FROM THE RENTAL OF VEHICLES

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Abstract. In this scientific thesis, the system of taxation of income from vehicle rental in Uzbekistan and the trend of change in the number of passenger cars owned by individuals; individual entrepreneurs (IE) carrying out passenger transport activities in light vehicles and the composition of taxes paid by them were analyzed.

Key words: property income of individuals, vehicles, light motor vehicles of individuals, tax burden.

Аннотация. В данной научной работе рассмотрена система налогообложения доходов от аренды транспортных средств в Узбекистане и динамика изменения количества легковых автомобилей, находящихся в собственности физических лиц; проанализированы индивидуальные предприниматели, осуществляющие пассажирские перевозки легковым автотранспортом, и состав уплачиваемых ими налогов.

Ключевые слова: имущественные доходы физических лиц, транспортные средства, легковые автомобили физических лиц, налоговая нагрузка.

In the improvement of property income taxation of individuals in Uzbekistan, the main attention should be focused on taxation of citizens' incomes from informal activities and elimination of tax evasion.

In recent years, one of the illegal incomes of natural persons in the republic is the income received in connection with the vehicle. It is known that the number of vehicles belonging to individuals in Uzbekistan is increasing year by year. We can see this in the table below (table 1).

Table 1. The trend of changes in the number of passenger cars owned by individuals in Uzbekistan[1]

№	Regions	2017 y.	2018 y.	2019 y.	2020 y.	2021 y.
1	Karakalpakstan R.	90 115	92 458	106 801	113 140	127 034
2	Andijan	149 769	154 189	164 448	192 944	206 076
3	Bukhara	161 385	163 580	165 546	180 478	196 858
4	Jizzakh	53 110	58 020	63 140	72 530	85 899
5	Kashkadarya	154 256	187 796	189 928	223 733	242 068
6	Navoi	65 562	71 752	72 122	75 039	89 526

7	Namangan	136 605	146 864	146 947	180 367	196 821
8	Samarkand	260 786	277 547	293 729	323 586	366 676
9	Surkhandarya	121 811	126 506	132 562	150 574	172 485
10	Syrdarya	34 744	41 084	45 611	60 803	60 803
11	Tashkent region	194 504	225 303	236 754	262 741	307 913
12	Ferghana	222 114	227 387	227 634	276 558	297 232
13	Khorezm	151 911	154 058	159 547	187 457	199 313
14	Tashkent city	336 835	345 641	405 652	467 176	503 030
Total for republic		2 133 507	2 272 185	2 410 421	2 767 126	3 051 734

The table shows that the number of passenger cars owned by individuals was 2,133,507 in 2017, 2,272,185 in 2018, 2,410,421 in 2019, 2,767,126 in 2020, and 3,051,734 in 2021. During this period, the number of vehicles owned by individuals increased by 918,227 or 43 percent. This, in turn, creates a source of income for individuals through passenger transportation.

According to the information of the State Tax Committee, the total number of vehicles taxed by tax authorities is 35,102. Of these, 1,321 citizens who transported passengers on lease to legal entities as individual entrepreneurs (hereinafter referred to as self-employed persons) and 33,781 are self-employed persons.

In the early years, only legal entities with a license were allowed to engage in passenger transportation activities. For this purpose, legal entities have rented vehicles of individuals. Based on the number of vehicles, a license for passenger transportation is obtained.

He also hired drivers to transport passengers in the vehicle. As a result, legal entities paid wages and income tax for employees, as well as social tax and rent and income tax for an individual's vehicle. This made the tax administration complicated and the tax burden was high. For this reason, individuals carried out the activity of transporting passengers by means of vehicles unofficially.

Based on this, in the following years, effective reforms aimed at easing the tax burden on income from passenger transport were implemented. In particular, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-5108 dated May 7, 2021, from May 15, 2021, IEs were also allowed to engage in the activity of transporting passengers in light motor vehicles with no more than 4 seats in addition to the driver.

In this case, transportation of passengers by light vehicles is carried out based on the license sheet. Self-employed carriers are not allowed to hire employees as part of the activity of transporting passengers by road.

It was decided that individual transporters will pay a fixed amount of personal income tax at the fixed rate for private transport companies engaged in the transportation of goods in vehicles capable of carrying up to 3 tons, i.e. 150,000 soums per month. In addition, social tax is paid in the amount of one times the amount of the basic calculation (currently 300,000 soums) for one month.

We pay attention to the amount of taxes paid by IEs carrying out passenger transport activities in light vehicles (Table 2).

Table 2. Structure of IEs carrying out passenger transport activities in light motor vehicles and taxes paid by them[2]

million soums

№	Regions	2021 y.			2022 y.		
		Number of IEs	Income tax	Social tax	Number of IEs	Income tax	Social tax
1	Karakalpakstan R.	632	438,8	474,9	1 321	818,3	1 042,4
2	Andijan	485	308,3	290,1	1 184	610,1	807,7
3	Bukhara	432	324,0	523,8	641	349,4	453,9
4	Jizzakh	250	182,3	257,0	508	276,3	368,2
5	Kashkadarya	512	354,0	380,2	1 096	719,7	916,6
6	Navoi	293	209,3	270,1	501	178,6	594,7
7	Namangan	131	175,0	295,1	308	150,1	175,9
8	Samarkand	951	693,8	1 002,7	1 513	915,8	1 212,4
9	Surkhandarya	917	658,5	817,9	1 466	1 076,9	1 428,5
10	Syrdarya	453	318,0	396,6	875	529,0	701,5
11	Tashkent region	578	423,0	574,1	853	559,1	755,1
12	Ferghana	364	249,0	330,2	681	426,8	438,8
13	Khorezm	197	143,3	196,5	385	181,8	223,9
14	Tashkent city	729	501,8	658,3	1 074	742,4	1 314,2
Total		6 924	4 978,8	6 467,6	12 406	7 534,3	10 433,8

As can be seen from the table, the number of public transportation companies carrying out the activity of transporting passengers in light motor vehicles was

6,924 in 2021 and 12,406 in 2022. In 2021, 4,978.8 million soums of income tax and 6,467,6 million soums of social tax were paid by these private companies, and in 2022, 7,534.3 million soums of income tax and 10,433.8 million soums of social tax were paid.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-311 dated July 7, 2022, from September 1, 2022 to the end of 2024, self-employed persons were allowed to engage in the activity of transporting passengers in light motor vehicles with no more than 4 seats except for the driver.

The activity of transporting passengers in light motor vehicles by self-employed persons is carried out on the basis of a license sheet. It was established that persons employed on the basis of an employment contract in other areas can simultaneously engage in the activity of transporting passengers by light motor vehicles while being registered as a self-employed person.

According to the data of Figure 1, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, 33,781 people are considered as self-employed persons carrying out the activity of transporting passengers in light motor vehicles.

According to Article 369 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, self-employed persons' incomes received as a result of labor activities are not included in the total income of individuals and are not taxed.

In order to calculate length of service, self-employed citizens voluntarily pay social tax in the amount of at least one times the amount of basic calculation per year.

Figure 1. Analysis of natural persons counted as self-employed persons carrying out the activity of passenger transport by light motor vehicles by region[3]

Pursuant to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-311 of July 7, 2022, the requirement for notarization of vehicle rental contracts

concluded between citizens and legal entities with a license to carry out passenger transportation activities from September 1, 2022 has been canceled and the state tax service authorities will inform them. system of electronic accounting was introduced.

The number of light motor vehicles of individuals accounted for by the State Tax Committee on the basis of transport lease agreements is 10,894. 299 of these vehicles are in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 2,456 in Andijan, 538 in Bukhara, 200 in Jizzakh, 733 in Kashkadarya, 205 in Navoi, 1,419 in Namangan, 595 in Samarkand, 448 in Surkhandarya, 89 in Syrdarya, 882 in Tashkent region. 1,755 were counted in Ferghana, 848 in Khorezm, 427 in Tashkent (Figure 2).

It can be seen that effective measures aimed at reducing the tax burden and improving the tax administration have been implemented in our country regarding the legalization of the income of individuals from vehicles. However, it is necessary to overcome some problems regarding taxation of these incomes.

Figure 2. Information on the number of light motor vehicles of individuals registered on the basis of transport lease agreements at the State Tax Committee[4]

In particular, the tax burden for 1 vehicle varies depending on the category of taxpayers. The amount of tax on the income received from 1 vehicle per month is 795.6 thousand soms for an average legal entity, 450.0 thousand soms for a self-employed person, and self-employed citizens are not taxed.

Therefore, the tax burden should be unified for all taxpayers. For this purpose, it is appropriate to cancel the minimum standard for cars rented by individuals and to introduce an income tax in the amount specified for IEs for individuals

who are considered as self-employed persons carrying out the activity of transporting passengers in light vehicles.

Also, it is necessary to introduce a system of 12 percent tax on the income of citizens at the source of payment through business entities (hereinafter referred to as aggregators) that provide interactive customer search services to passenger carriers.

References:

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